

Paper 7

Post-Pandemic Entry Level Indian Private Banking Jobs

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Abstract

The unprecedented impact of COVID 19 has left a very bleak impact on the graduate job markets and industry. With private commercial banks themselves battling for profits, any new manpower addition at these times especially greenhorns in any forms seemed challenging and unlikely. Currently, uncertainty made room in graduate minds regarding banking work and new developments they heard at their universities regarding banking industry during lockdown and how to adjust to the new normal to seek a job and work in a private commercial banks post pandemic. Hence, this paper explores what will be the new nature, mode and choice of work for graduate greenhorns beginning their career path post lockdown in private banking industry. Futuristic analysis is a research art of contemplating future by using data mining methodologies on huge current available information and arranging in systematic interpretation of probabilistic real future formats through data elements, utilized in this study for analysis.

Key Words : Post-pandemic Banking Jobs, Banking Jobs Post-covid, Predictive Analysis, Banking Job Freshers, Private Banking Jobs.

1. Introduction :

Profitability focused Indian Private banking industry witnessed unprecedented growth until covid19 outbreak. As the entire economy came to a halt, an intimidating slowdown was imminent making entire scenario worse. However, the silver lining of this crisis is that the unprecedented times have given the immense opportunity for the sector to bring about a fundamental change in the way that it functions. In recent years, India also witnessed a phenomenal rise in the number of private banking establishments. As a result, these establishments with their clear vision and mission created banking jobs on a massive scale for entry level graduates. In addition to top management school hiring, they also handpicked university freshers and other lateral able candidates through direct recruitment. With the outbreak of pandemic 2020 however, there was a sunken dive of new entrants to the private banking industry owing to dipped profits especially during lockdown owing to uncertainty. However, these private banks quickly found space to reinvent themselves and test newer business models that are more digitally-driven. By leveraging advanced technologies and digitizing existing set of offerings, banks altered age-old processes with newer, more optimized workflows. Well, with economy poised to return to new normal post pandemic due to various regulatory efforts from stakeholders, the hiring is slowly expected to recover as private banking businesses is poised to grow back steady in coming time period. Therefore, this study attempts to uncover the state of entry level hiring at private banks post pandemic.

2. Objectives of the Research :

The primary aim of this study is to educate the student and graduate aspirants about the prevailing situations at the entry level private banking job market at pandemic. The study works to bring out to inform the entrants about post pandemic on skill sets to be possessed owing to shifted new bank working

normal. Finally, study explores further research element in the area and draw the scope in private banking job market.

3. Research Methodology

The data for this study was collected through direct interview with select private bankers as well as secondary sources like web articles ET BFSI. Gathered Data is analysed through envisioning responses of practicing bankers for arriving at current state of future for entry level private banking jobs. Scenario forecasting based on data is further deployed to conclude the study.

4. Analysis and Interpretation :

Based upon gathered data, the Indian private banking sector is currently recruiting in following methodologies which is slated to continue considering the state of Pandemic :

(a) Virtual Hiring Process :

It is found that Banks and Finance companies have begun hiring virtually. Support teams like HR, Legal & Compliance, and Technology are operating from home and right from recruitment to on-boarding of new employees is happening online as per Mr. R Venkatesh, Head Operations, Technology & HR, DCB Bank featured in ET BFSI [13].

(b) Remote Work from Home :

Banks are also conducting psychometric tests of the candidates for the best results remotely. The HR head also asserted, post lockdown DCB Bank will have a balanced policy for their employees which includes an apt Work from Home [WFH] numbers. Axis Bank also announced their planned recruitment of 1000 employees remotely both under full time and part time project based temporary gig scheme as reported by ET BFSI [14]

The Indian banking industry has been witnessing a speedy transition from people-driven to machines controlled in the past few years which has gained momentum during pandemic. The technological development, which has made banking easier, has also led to a increase in the hiring of tech savvy staff at banks. Although there has been hiring, the nature of skill sets required is changing with a lot more focus on

the new IT Talent. Even top public sector banks are scouting for technical and IT staff at entry level to meet the requirements of managing digital and online banking boosted due to bank from home.

5. Findings

The research found following avenues for fresh graduates to enter into Private Banking Jobs during or post pandemic :

(1) Through Academic Route

Fresh Graduate Aspirants can join NIIT / Manipal School of Banking for PGDBFO (Post Graduate Degree in Banking and Finance) [15] where entry job is embedded in form of a branch work internship and class room training (now online) by direct bank trainers pertaining to operations, regulations and industry behaviour post pandemic. Aspiring students can also join university embedded programs like Srinivas University MBA in banking and finance who hold internship placement MoU with Private Banks through a third-party administrator Times Pro Limited [16]. Here in these programs, candidates obtain provisional offer letter from banks even before the candidate joins the program through initial

interviews coached and trained by the institutions. These programs blend theory and stipend paid practical internship at associated placement offering workplace of banks with emphasis on real job training. Performing Students are offered final placements. Currently, these placements assisted courses are taught on Online Virtual Mode.

(2) Direct approach to branch or through website career section

Students or fresh graduates can approach private bank websites directly to explore enrolling “Gig-a-Opportunities’ for project-based assignments and also give virtual video interviews for full time work.

(3) Employee Referral

Entry level graduates wanting to enter private banking sector can request their friends, college seniors and acquaintances for referrals to gain interview opportunities during the Pandemic. This method of recruiting remains very popular as HRM sections may not be able to conduct open hiring due to pandemic norms, lockdowns and other restrictions.

However, pandemic times has resulted in the operational efficiency of the banks, which is expected to surge as well. This shift is partly credited to the now imperative push of digitization. Customers have taken a liking to the idea of mobile and internet banking with increased installations of ATMs within and outside their city quarters. Such 24/7 live facilities put convenience at the centre of the user experience and introduce a new level of customer service in banking driving the job requirement even further up. To date, the chunk of the individuals hired in the BFSI sector has been from commerce or engineering backgrounds. With technological advancements, the creation of new jobs is emerging. There will be plenty of jobs like data analysts, app developers, artificial intelligence experts for people who are up-to-date with these technologies. An additional opportunity will open up for people with exceptional soft skills. Customer retention is the basis of the Private Banking Sector and people who have the skills for this job would have plenty of opportunities in the Industry in coming future. The most required specific skills are proficiency in sales, stock market knowledge, mathematical aptitude, mutual fund awareness, and knowledge about banking operations. Other soft skills like good financial business communication skills and confidence will also add value to entry level curriculum vitae. Automation, Artificial Intelligence and Robotics is also making way in customer operations.

Traditional jobs such as passbook updating, cash deposit, verification of know-your-customer details, salary uploads are going digital increasing job redundancies. The likes of Axis Bank, ICICI Bank and HDFC Bank are pushing the boundaries of technology by implementing robotics to centralise operations and for quicker turnarounds in things like loan processing and selling financial products to customers. This reduces the need for a manual worker at the office beneficial during a pandemic.

6. Suggestions

The industrial interaction in above research formed the basis to advance following recommendations :

- The Job Seeking graduates in Private Banking Sector must be able to develop online virtual meeting conduct and attending capabilities in compliance, IT and HR.
- The Graduates offered for frontline customer facing branch operations must be able to take risks to work in pandemic affected areas as Banking comes under essential services.

- The freshers must be able to get trained remotely on banking products and services from home and work. Students planning a career in Banking sector in the future as requested to pursue studies in Financial Technologies (Fintech)

7. Conclusion

The Digital and Online Remote banking industry in India is growing rapidly due to Pandemic and actively looking for fresh graduates to join them with new age skills. Many of Private banks also are contemplating salary hikes and bonus rollouts. Therefore, based on the suggestions, fresh graduate job seekers in this space are appealed to develop relevant life skills like patience, endurance, resiliency, perseverance and persistence to sustain in pandemic work environment of Indian private banking industry.

References

- [1] Hockett, R. (2020). Spread the Fed: Distributed Central Banking in Pandemic and Beyond. *Va. L. & Bus. Rev.*, 15, 89.
- [2] Ramasamy, D. (2020). Impact Analysis in Banking, Insurance and Financial services industry due to COVID-19 Pandemic. *Pramana Research Journal*, 10(8).
- [3] Singh, J., & Bodla, B. S. (2020). Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown impact on India's banking sector: a systemic literature review. *COVID-19 pandemic: a global challenge*, 21-32.
- [4] Kulińska-Sadłocha, E., Marcinkowska, M., & Szambelańczyk, J. (2020). The impact of pandemic risk on the activity of banks based on the Polish banking sector in the face of COVID-19. *Bezpieczny Bank*, (2 (79)), 31-59.
- [5] Łasak, P. (2021). The commercial banking sector in Eurozone after the pandemic: the paths to recovery. *European Research Studies Journal*, 24(1).
- [6] Moulton, T., Bourne, P. A., Graham, D., Jarrett, R., Edwards, M., Peterkin, V. M., ... & Charles, M. (2020). Online Banking among Jamaicans during the 2020 COVID-19 Pandemic. *The Corporate International* [ISSN: 2581-6438 (online)], 4(2).
- [7] Goodhart, C., Masciandaro, D., & Ugolini, S. (2021). *Pandemic recession, helicopter money and central banking: Venice, 1630*.
- [8] Ban, C. (2021). Central Banking in Pandemic Times. *Global Perspectives*, 2(1).
- [9] Rahman, M. H., Mutsuddi, P., Roy, S. K., Al-Amin, M., & Jannat, F. (2020). Performance Efficiency Evaluation of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Application in Human Resource Management during COVID-19 Pandemic: A Study on Banking Industry of Bangladesh. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 46-56.
- [10] Vorayot, L. (2020). *THAI RETAIL CUSTOMER BEHAVIOR ON INTENTION OF USING MOBILE BANKING ACCORDING TO A PANDEMIC OF COVID19* (Doctoral dissertation, Mahidol University).
- [11] Lee, K. Y. M., binti Zaidi, N. S., & Wen, C. C. (2020). Technical Analysis and Malaysian Banking Sector during COVID-19 Pandemic. *UNIMAS Review of Accounting and Finance*, 4(1), 41-46.
- [12] Rodrigues Pinto, A., Alves dos Santos, T., & Dai Prá Martens, C. (2021). Impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on digital entrepreneurship in banking institutions of Brazil: An analysis in the light of isomorphic forces. *Estudios Gerenciales*, 37(158), 113-125.
- [12] DBS Bank Indonesia (2021). The important role of banking in post-pandemic economic recovery | Bahasa. https://www.dbs.com/newsroom/The_important_role_of_banking_in_post_pandemic_economic_recovery

[13] Deth Amul (2020). Multifunctionality is the way forward to remain in the job: DCB Bank. <https://bfsi.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/banking/multifunctionality-is-the-way-forward-to-remain-in-the-job-dcb-bank/76253912>

[14] <https://www.livemint.com/companies/news/axis-bank-launches-hiring-initiative-gig-a-opportunities-to-hire-up-to-1-000-11597918579445.html>

https://www.dbs.com/newsroom/The_important_role_of_banking_in_post_pandemic_economic_recovery

[15] NIIT (n.d.) Post Graduate Diploma in Sales and Relationship Banking. <https://www.niit.com/india/graduates/banking-and-finance/post-graduate-diploma-sales-and-relationship-banking>

[16] Srinivas University (n.d.). MBA in Banking and Finance in association with TimesPro Ltd. <https://srinivasuniversity.edu.in/College-Of-Management-And-Commerce/PG-Courses/MBA-Banking-Finance>
